

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
Twenty-fifth Annual Report/1981

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One Dupont Circle, NW • Washington, DC 20036

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . . Paris: 1588*. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, which explained that "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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1. As of November 1980

2. Mr. Coles was elected to succeed Mr. Kempner at the November 1980 annual meeting.

3. Until January, 1981

4. Until December, 1980

5. Until August, 1980

6. Until December, 1980

7. As of January, 1981

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8. As of March, 1981

9. As of March, 1981

10. As of January, 1981

Preface

“What, then, are these ‘problems of libraries’ to which the Council’s activities are directed?” Verner Clapp asked this question in CLR’s first annual report, and for twenty-five years since that time the Council has worked to identify “problems” and to encourage its own staff and many others to find solutions. In part, at least, as a result of CLR programs and complementary work by other organizations, the research library of 1981 is in many ways very different from what it was in 1956. It is physically larger, its services are much expanded, it is more complex and costly, its technology is transformed, and it is more influential in terms of its contribution to teaching and research. Also, it still has problems.

While a twenty-fifth annual report might be the place to reflect on a quarter century of problems and progress, we have chosen not to do so. The main text of this report concentrates on activities of the twenty-fifth year alone. These preliminary pages will consider the agenda for the twenty-sixth year and beyond.

In March, 1981, the Council’s Board agreed that a review of CLR programs and methods was in order. A Special Committee was established to begin the task, and its report to the Board is the basis for planning to be done during CLR’s twenty-sixth year.¹ During the remainder of 1981 and through the first half of 1982, CLR staff and board members, along with others we hope to enlist, will work to refine our plans for the decade ahead and to find support for the work to be done.

1. The Committee was chaired by Ruth Davis, a CLR Board member, and included Robert Vosper, also a Board member, Robert O’Neil (President, University of Wisconsin) and Neil Rudenstine (Provost, Princeton University).

At this writing, it is too early to be specific about CLR's future plans. There are major areas that need further study and review before program decisions can be reached. But it seems important to give some sense of the directions in which we are looking to underscore both the stability and the dynamic quality of this twenty-five-year-old enterprise.

It is unlikely that the Council will turn abruptly away from any of its present major program areas. On review, they seem sound, momentum is strong, results thus far are good and future prospects even better. The Bibliographic Service Development Program is now established as a major force in promoting a comprehensive computerized bibliographic system for the nation. By providing some funds and by pressing for improved coordination in both development and operation, we are moving toward a flexible and effective bibliographic structure that will offer complete coverage and help assure reasonable access. Similarly, CLR will continue to encourage, when it can, activities designed to enhance the national capacity to assemble and preserve resources for research and scholarship. Newly expanded programs to promote research librarianship as a profession and to refine professional education and training methods will continue, as will long-established programs to improve library management.

What is likely to happen in our twenty-sixth year is that the Council's portfolio will expand. New efforts to incorporate research libraries more effectively into a fast-changing information environment can be anticipated. Related matters concerning library costs and funding for library services also will require attention.

The report of the Special Committee to the CLR Board is both precise and powerful. After reflecting on the cumulative effects of economic pressures, technologically induced change, and severe managerial stresses, the Committee observed that the library of the 1980's is not emerging as evolutionary, based merely on incremental changes to its 1970's predecessor; rather, the library of the 1980's appears destined to be a manifestation of new technological and economic realities and of new expectations not realizable by simple extrapolations from the library of the 1970's.

Further, the Special Committee concluded that the technological and economic issues which dominated the 1970's will give way to serious and in some cases, vexing policy issues. The enlightened resolution of these policy issues will, in turn, provide guidance for establishing needed library practices, library services, cooperative arrangements among libraries, and the determination of costing and pricing policies.

In the view of the Committee, the survival, much less the fate of the academic and research library in the 1980's as society's primary intellectual resource, appears to depend upon the outcome of a single policy issue. This issue arises from differing perceptions of the library as an instrument for public service. These diverse perceptions lead inevitably to varying views of who should pay for library services. The issue is:

Can the library continue to provide its services as an essentially free public good? Can it do so while simultaneously providing the increasing diversity

and improved quality of services made possible by technological advances? Can it provide such free public services in a market which otherwise distributes and prices its services in keeping with user or customer demand?

In addition, the Committee identified seven related issues to which it believes attention should be directed:

1. What should be the national commitment to library services as a public and free good?
2. What should libraries offer in terms of diversity of information media and of library services?
3. How and where should information and library services be combined, provided, and marketed?
4. What should be the infrastructure of the library community for policy, economic, and service purposes?
5. How should the introduction and diffusion of technology be paced, controlled, and financed by libraries?
6. How should the user-library relationship be configured so as to enhance a mutually supportive arrangement?
7. What should comprise "librarianship" and "information service" to define a career field for research librarians?

These are valid questions. For the Council, the key issue is not *what* the answers are, but rather *how* CLR might be of assistance to research librarians, to university officers, and most of all to those who use and depend on libraries as the search for answers proceeds.

What CLR should do and how the Council must change to add these new and difficult topics to its present agenda are the questions now under consideration. Before the end of the twenty-sixth year, we plan to have not only those answers but to have work under way on the substance of these matters as well.

W.J.H.

Program Highlights

Measured in terms of active grants and contracts, the Council's twenty-fifth year was its busiest. New awards totalling nearly \$2,000,000 were made. Echoing recent years, bibliographic undertakings dominated the new grants. However, as a sign of expanding interests, the professional education program was a strong second. As always, the full range of current projects mirrored concerns and interests in the academic and research library world.

Certain recurring themes are readily identifiable. The Council has always tried to assist projects that benefit the profession as a whole, as suggested by its support for the publication by the American Library Association of *American Library Laws*, and current research on leaders in American academic librarianship coordinated by Wayne Wiegand at the University of Kentucky. International programs, too, have always been an important concern. While Council financial commitment in this area has somewhat diminished relative to overall activity, its interest in projects that further library development throughout the world has remained a major focus since 1956.¹

The Council's most important current interests in terms of financial commitment are the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP), now in its third year, and the new Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship Program (PETREL). Both stem from long felt needs for improvement in national bibliographic services and professional education. The two projects reflect both continuity and change. CLR has

1. For the purpose of providing background information to accompany descriptions of current projects, this report draws upon material from earlier CLR annual reports.

supported efforts to improve bibliographic services for twenty-five years, and similarly, interest in improving professional education also dates from many earlier projects. However, by organizing diffused efforts into cohesive programs, a new emphasis has been given to these particular areas.

The focus on library management remains an important concern. Broadly defined, management extends to library operations, services and collections, all of which have received CLR attention in recent years. Support for the Association of Research Libraries, Office of Management Studies, and aid for small schools through projects such as the collection evaluation manual undertaken by the Associated Colleges of the Midwest provide individual libraries with the means to assess their own programs and improve their operations. Further, almost all libraries benefit from the BSDP concentration on a nationwide bibliographic record service and from the PETREL Program's focus on recruiting and training students specifically for academic and research library service.

In planning and operating its programs, the Council has received assistance from many groups and individuals within and outside librarianship. Their advice and counsel is valuable, not only in evaluating proposals and establishing program priorities, but also in accomplishing an increasing amount of the work required to deal with a variety of complex technical matters to assure program implementation.

During fiscal 1981, CLR paid special attention to the improvement of communication among librarians, scholars and university officers. The Council funded an April, 1981 meeting organized by the Association of Research Libraries and the American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities to find ways to improve communication between libraries and the scholarly community. Scholars, librarians and association officials who attended the meeting agreed on two actions. Noting that faculty frequently lack information about research library matters, the group suggested experimental distribution of *Library Issues*, a monthly newsletter produced by the editor of *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, to all faculty members at selected campuses. The Council has partially funded this activity. Participants also recommended bringing library issues to the attention of scholarly organizations through more participation by librarians in annual meetings of those organizations, and agreed to work with scholarly associations to implement this suggestion.

Another cooperative project is the CLR/Association of American Universities effort to examine major issues facing U.S. research libraries. In February, 1981, the two organizations brought twelve university officials, librarians, and foundation executives together to discuss research librarianship. The group identified five high priority concerns: bibliographic data bases and the problems of access to bibliographic information; resource sharing and the attendant problems of collecting, preserving and making collections available; preservation of deteriorating books and other materials; technological applications; and research librarianship itself.

Five task forces were subsequently asked to explore these topics in detail and to produce reports proposing a limited number of specific actions for prompt attention. A conference for library directors, university administrators, scholars, and others is planned to review the recommendations and suggest appropriate action.

The need to work with scholars and academic officers, and with the major academic, educational and library associations has been implicit in many CLR activities. "Cooperation" is a CLR byword, but possibly it deserves even more attention, and more explicit recognition. CLR clearly will require the assistance of a wider constituency in the future, to assure a better understanding of university-library relationships and to help achieve objectives important to scholarship, research and teaching.

Bibliographic Services

There have been many changes in bibliographic processes and services during the last twenty-five years. Moreover, from the vantage point of the present, the pace of change continues to accelerate. Yet as far back as 1956, libraries felt the need to address the "information explosion" by exploiting technology. The sense that libraries had helped create the age of automation but had gained little from it was one factor that prompted the establishment of CLR by the Ford Foundation. From the beginning, technological assistance for bibliographic processes and services was a major element of the CLR program. The Council's first report expressed the need to concentrate on "the exploration of technological means to solve problems that confront libraries in their service to scholarship and research."¹

By 1970, major bibliographic obstacles remained, even though automation of some library processes enhanced certain aspects of bibliographic control. A wistful note in the Council's fourteenth *Annual Report* hypothesized a different world in which "the United States might have a single library system wherein the optimum degree of centralization would insure the optimum use of resources to provide the best possible services to library clientele." There also would be a "single national data base in machine-readable form encompassing all types of library materials." However, the report concluded that the funds required for such a system were not available, and even if they were, a system of the type described probably could not be built, given the political realities and the rudimentary organization of available data.²

1. Council on Library Resources, Inc. *Annual Report* I:10

2. *Ibid.*, XIV:17-18

Nevertheless, the report noted that cooperation and the consequent elimination of duplicate efforts was a realistic alternative to a single national data base. CLR hoped to fit together existing efforts and encourage new ones. The cornerstone of the system was to be—and is—national bibliographic control: preparing standardized records and making them available economically, in either machine-readable or manual form, to all libraries. With the development of a machine-readable cataloging system at the Library of Congress, the MEDLARS system at the National Library of Medicine, and efforts to create a national serials data base, movement toward the provision of national library services clearly had begun.

More than ten years ago, criteria for a national data base were firmly established. They included—and still do—comprehensiveness, authority, accessibility, timeliness, and standardization—all at reasonable cost.³ Much of the Council's work since that time has consisted of requesting, suggesting, encouraging, catalyzing, organizing and funding projects that might become parts of a national system. CLR has supported developmental work for networks and consortia, assisted programs that involve individuals and groups in cooperative efforts to build machine-readable data bases, and provided grants for efforts to develop standards—both national and international—to facilitate the exchange of bibliographic data.

By the late 1970's, a number of CLR-assisted groups had established related goals. Refining those efforts into a coordinated program with a common objective then became essential to assure productive cooperation and to enlist new collaborative efforts.

Bibliographic Service Development Program

In 1978, CLR launched the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) to coordinate bibliographic efforts already under way, and to channel funds to new projects. Supported by seven major foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities,⁴ the BSDP's goals are to provide effective bibliographic services for all who need them; to improve bibliographic products; and to stabilize costs (in constant dollars) of many bibliographic processes in individual libraries. Wherever possible, the program uses existing resources. This implies cooperation by a number of groups and individuals, including the major producers of bibliographic records.

One prediction of the 1970 *Annual Report* has not changed. It still is unlikely that a single national data base, located in a single place, ever will exist. Linking the existing major bibliographic data bases seems more likely, and the BSDP has directed efforts toward that goal. Working closely with the Library of Congress, the Online Computer Library Center

3. *Ibid.*, XIV:18-20.

4. The foundations are: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, the Commonwealth Fund, the Ford Foundation, the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

(OCLC, Inc.), the Research Libraries Group, Inc. and the Washington Library Network, participants in BSDP activities identify and carry out tasks directed toward improving access to bibliographic information. A Program Committee advises the Council on ongoing projects and new initiatives.⁵

During the past fiscal year, the BSDP made more grants than in any previous year. Thirty-eight grants and contracts were active, and funding of more than \$1,000,000 was awarded for twenty-five new projects. Details of BSDP project activities to date have been summarized in the *Bibliographic Service Development Program Report, 1978-1980*. Expectations for future bibliographic developments are described in the program document *Bibliographic Targets for 1984*.

Standards and Guides. A major requirement for bibliographic record sharing is a common understanding of the intellectual content of the records and agreement on their organization. Standards operate to assure consistency and to facilitate record communication, processing and storage. Many BSDP efforts are devoted to helping formulate national and international guidelines and standards.

In 1979, the BSDP formed a Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards, which includes representatives from research libraries, the major shared cataloging services, the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and the Council staff. The committee advises the Library of Congress on the interpretation of the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* (AACR-2) and the impact of these decisions on shared cataloging activities. The group also provides advice on the creation of manuals to guide the application of the rules to specialized materials such as newspapers, maps, archives and rare books.

A related effort was the Council's 1979 grant to Sue A. Dodd, associate research librarian at the Institute for Research in Social Science at the University of North Carolina, to prepare the manual: *Cataloging Machine-Readable Data Files: An Interpretive Manual*. Rules for cataloging data files appear in chapter 9 of the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*. However, few catalogers are familiar with the medium or its applications. Dodd's work is intended to provide guidelines for the use of the rules, and examples and interpretations of cataloging for this medium that would otherwise not be available.

The BSDP has also commissioned papers on institutions identification codes and holdings statements. Holdings statements are the part of a bibliographic record that indicates which libraries own particular items. The individual libraries are listed by means of acronyms or other identifiers.

5. Members of the Program Committee are: Henriette Avram, Library of Congress, Joan Gotwals, University of Pennsylvania, James Govan, University of North Carolina, Carol F. Ishimoto, Harvard University, Frederick G. Kilgour, OCLC, Inc., Edward E. Shaw, Research Libraries Group, Inc., and Roderick G. Swartz, Washington State Library.

Standardizing these identifiers would facilitate access to location information for researchers and interlibrary loan librarians. In 1980, contracts were awarded to Howard and Patricia Harris and to Richard Anable to produce papers on the two topics.

The Harrises' paper, titled "Refinements and Design Considerations for a Standard Means of Library Identification," was completed during the past year. The authors review current standards efforts in this area, and present recommendations for a standard. They also evaluate a series of design alternatives for identification codes.

Richard Anable explored the use of holdings statements as external indicators of which materials are owned by a library and as the library's internal record of items owned. His paper, titled "An Investigation of the Holdings Statement Requirements Within a Location System," addresses both location and local inventory control functions of holdings statements. Anable states that because there is an increasing need to share resources, both the means of identifying what is owned at a particular library and what parts are owned are important to building an effective location system. He recommends that local inventory control of holdings be incorporated into any holdings system design.

Closely linked to the design of standards for holdings statement information is a particularly important and difficult to resolve problem: simultaneous serials cancellations. In an attempt to develop a mechanism to preserve the last copy of a title in a region, the Pittsburgh Regional Library Center proposed, and received CLR funding for, a prototype system for standardizing serial cancellations procedures. Project participants are developing methods for recording and communicating cancellations through an online union list.

Related to BSDP objectives is another area of standards activity that has been supported from the Council's general funds since 1961: the work of the American National Standards Committee Z39. The committee is part of the American National Standards Institute, a federation of technical, professional, and trade organizations and commercial firms, which acts as a national clearinghouse and coordinator for voluntary standards in this country. Committee Z39 bears responsibility for standards in the library and information sciences and related publishing practices. This year, based upon the committee's progress toward becoming self-supporting, the Council phased out direct operational funding for the committee. However, it continues to support standards activity through BSDP projects and work with other groups.

Networks. During the past ten to fifteen years, a number of organizations have been formed to provide bibliographic products and services to libraries. Prominent among these organizations are about two dozen regional networks. Encompassing particular geographic areas, the networks are of various types, and they owe their existence, financing and defined scope to

different kinds of governing instruments. Many of them were established to facilitate access to bibliographic data bases and associated services.

CLR's interest in the role of networks as part of the evolving nationwide bibliographic framework prompted a contract with James E. Rush and Norman Stevens to report on current network configuration. Their paper, titled "Issues Relative to the Roles of State and Multi-State Networks in the Evolving Nationwide Bibliographic Network," has been completed and distributed to networks for comments. The authors visited or contacted state and multi-state networks and national library associations, institutions and individuals. The report incorporates many of the concerns of those interviewed.

Bibliographic Data Bases. The Online Computer Library Center (OCLC, Inc.), The Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG), and the Washington Library Network (WLN), together provide several thousand libraries with online access to millions of bibliographic records. As *de facto* components of a national information system, their data bases, along with those of the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and other agencies, are the major bibliographic resources which need somehow to be made accessible to the nation's library users. The Council, through the BSDP, has been exploring issues that relate to linking data bases, and in September 1979, CLR signed a contract with Battelle-Columbus Laboratories to investigate the feasibility and effects of alternate approaches to this end.

In the Battelle-Columbus study, over 250 public and academic libraries were asked for data on their experiences with the services of the shared cataloging systems. Battelle also conducted "hit-rate" studies to calculate the benefits of linking for shared cataloging, interlibrary loan verification, and reference searching. The final report, *Linking the Bibliographic Utilities: Benefits and Costs*, recommended that the Library of Congress, OCLC, Inc., the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN), and the Washington Library Network develop online links. The Council subsequently issued an analysis of the report titled *Linking Bibliographic Data Bases: A Discussion of the Battelle Technical Report*.

For the linking study, Battelle developed an interactive computer model called BIBLINK. The model was designed to assist the analysis of three types of links: direct tape delivery, "native" mode, and "translation" mode. A "native" mode link would require library users to know the command languages and structures used by all of the linked systems. In the "translation" mode, the computers automatically translate one system's command language into that of another system. Using additional BSDP funds, Battelle augmented the model and prepared a user guide so that it can be used to experiment with a variety of assumptions and data.

The Council subsequently issued another contract to Battelle to provide both a one-day orientation to the BIBLINK model and a four-month trial period during which BIBLINK would be available for use by library school

trainees via remote terminals. Held in March, 1981, the orientation session was attended by 15 library school faculty members and representatives of networks and utilities.

Data Base Structure. In September 1979, CLR sponsored a meeting of the shared cataloging services and the national libraries to discuss the need for a nationwide authority file service. An authority file acts as a dictionary, or thesaurus, for the bibliographic data bases it controls. The file contains authorized and alternate forms of personal and institutional names and subject terms. The system ensures that all relevant items can be found under accepted, standardized terminology. The current absence of such consistency among systems is a major obstacle to the effective exchange of bibliographic data in machine-readable form.

Representatives attending the 1979 meeting agreed that the establishment of a comprehensive name authority file was both technically possible and highly desirable. Subsequently, the Council funded a proposal from the Research Libraries Group, Inc. and the Washington Library Network for a two-year investigation of the technical capability required to link their authority file systems. The Library of Congress joined in planning and coordinating project activities. The major objectives of the so-called Linked Authority Systems Project (LASP) are to establish requirements and develop specifications for the hardware and software required for telecommunications and machine interchange of records. When the work is completed, each network will continue to operate its own authority control system, but also will be able to share authority records with other networks.

In order to achieve long-range goals of linking bibliographic networks to each other and to local libraries that are members of networks, it is necessary to establish communication protocols to be used by all participants. CLR has granted funds to Northwestern University to develop a means of computer-to-computer interchange of information. This application level protocol development will include several kinds of interchanges: sending textual messages between systems, transmitting records from one system to another, and individual search and retrieval of records from one system's data base in response to a query from another system.

Technical requirements for an authority system are only part of the BSDP effort to implement an authority file service for libraries. The accuracy, consistency and overall quality of the records also must be considered. The Library of Congress (LC) name authority file is considered the basis for the projected comprehensive authority file. LC staff participation in planning, and its effort to convert more than 100,000 LC name authority records to machine-readable form have been supported by CLR. In addition, Council funding made it possible for a U.S. representative from LC to attend an International Standards Organization meeting on an international authority system.

In order to assist the establishment of an integrated authority system, the Council formed a Task Force on a Name Authority File Service, which includes representatives of organizations participating in the LASP project and others. The nine-member group is formulating guidelines and requirements for the service. Task Force recommendations appeared in an April, 1981 report, *Requirements Statement for the Name Authority File Service*.

The document consists of three parts: background information on the project, specification of the general and technical requirements for the Service, and proposals for methods to ensure quality control. The purposes of the Service are:

To collect and maintain authority data for names, titles and series.

To record and maintain the relationships between and among headings for names, titles, and series.

To ensure integrity of heading forms.

To provide query access to authority data.

The report further specifies that the Service must incorporate data definitions identical to or comparable with those specified in *Authorities: A MARC Format*, and must accept and produce data in this format. Also, the file must be able to be used by a large number of institutions, even though some operations will be restricted to the institutions designated as contributing sources. The latter institutions will be responsible for creating and maintaining data in the file.

Subject Access. While name authority file work is now at a relatively advanced stage, many questions relating to subject file access need attention. The Council has funded some projects that promise to improve subject control. One grant went to Iowa State University to design and construct a computer-produced printed index to provide better access to the university library's reference collection. Another grant, to the American Association of Law Libraries, assisted the group to identify steps required to implement a national law network (LAWNET).

Subject files are unlike name authority files in that they are more specialized and less likely to be combined into a single comprehensive file. It is possible that a series of subject files, each designed to meet the needs of specialized user groups, will develop. If this occurs, an important task will be to "map" these files; that is, to draw attention to equivalent terms within them.

In its exploration of these possibilities, the BSDP has funded several projects. A small planning grant to the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute for work on a thesaurus of art and architecture terms contributed to furthering work on subject access. In 1981, Dora Crouch, Pat Molholt and Toni Peterson completed *Indexing in Art and Architecture: An Investigation*. The authors identified eleven projects that may provide a beginning for a standard indexing vocabulary for the two fields.

As a step toward examining general subject access to materials in research libraries, the BSDP contracted with Carol Mandel and Judith Herschman to produce a paper evaluating subject access systems in relation to the needs of researchers and scholars. The paper, titled "Subject Access in the Online Catalog" discusses research findings that relate to the problems and prospects of providing online subject access.

Related to determining the parameters of subject access is an ongoing effort to help shared cataloging services identify growth trends within the MARC data base. Martha Williams of the University of Illinois Coordinated Science Laboratory is engaged in determining trends and relationships in MARC records, including frequency distributions of records by LC class and data base characteristics such as field lengths. The results of her investigation are expected to be useful to those engaged in establishing computer capacities for network use.

Products and Services. The data that will be provided as a result of BSDP projects is intended to serve as a building block for library services. The kinds of products and services that are required and the user groups that need them are the subject of ongoing research funded through the program.

Some libraries now provide public access to a bibliographic data base through online terminals. OCLC and RLG during 1980 conducted a study of the problems and priorities involved in access to bibliographic data bases, and produced a report titled *Online Public Access to Library Bibliographic Data Bases*. The report identified four topics for further research: user requirements and behavior, the performance of existing public access systems, methods for cost management, and computing and system linkages.

Based on the report, CLR made grants and contracts to six different groups to coordinate their efforts on a project to evaluate online public access catalogs. J. Matthews & Associates, OCLC, the Research Libraries Group, the University of California, Division of Library Automation (DLA), the University of Toronto Library Automated System (UTLAS) and the Library of Congress are working together in a multi-phase project.

The major objectives of the evaluation are to produce comparative data on existing systems and to provide information to guide future online catalog development. The requirements of those who use the catalogs and the performance of existing catalogs relative to user expectations and needs are the subjects of the data collection effort. Phase one includes the development of data collection instruments and standard forms. The instruments and forms then will be refined and tested. Data collection and analysis and the preparation of preliminary and final reports will follow. Funding for these activities totals over \$400,000. A number of public, college and university libraries are cooperating in the data collection efforts.

Association of Research Libraries Microform Project

A BSDP grant of \$20,000 was awarded in March, 1981, to the Association of Research Libraries for a two-year project designed to improve bibliographic access to microform collections in American and Canadian libraries. The prospect of adding to the national bibliographic files a number of retrospective records for items included in microform projects but never cataloged separately fulfills a long-held desire to make these materials more readily available. A major concern is to assure that national standards are accepted and followed and to make the records available to all libraries that wish to use them. The project emphasizes building on existing resources, coordinating efforts between the library and publishing communities, and the shared bibliographic services, and where possible, facilitating cooperative projects planned or under way.

CONSER

The Conversion of Serials project (CONSER) is a cooperative file-building effort that has resulted in a national serials data base. That data base now extends beyond the United States, since the National Library of Canada has joined in the CONSER activities. The Council funded and managed CONSER during the mid-seventies, but OCLC has since assumed the management role. The project has served to confirm a belief basic to the development of a nationwide bibliographic network: that data base quality can be maintained even if responsibility for supplying records is shared.

In 1978, the Council granted funds to the National Library of Canada to assist publication (in computer output microfiche) of the authenticated records from the CONSER project. This development enabled non-OCLC members to have access to the records. NLC plans to issue annual supplements to the CONSER microfiche.

The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada are responsible for the authentication of records contributed to the CONSER data base by the eighteen participating libraries. Authentication—certifying the completeness and correctness of bibliographic data input by participating libraries—has been slow, and until early 1980, only half the records in the file had been authenticated. OCLC has periodically produced magnetic tape copies of all records in the data base for the Library of Congress. In turn, LC has made the file available for purchase. The most recent of these “snapshot” files was produced in July, 1981. Records for file changes made after that date are also available on tape through the Library of Congress.

CLR has provided some assistance for a project to catalog the extensive journal collections of the Boston Theological Institute, a consortium that includes nine libraries holding over 7,000 unique titles. Completed this year, the project relied upon CONSER machine-readable data for con-

version of the union list of serials. The Lilly Endowment and Arthur Vining Davis Foundation also contributed to the project.

The Council continues to support telecommunication costs for some of the CONSER participants, in addition to the foregoing activities.

Cataloging in Publication

Supplying bibliographic information within a publication is an idea that dates back more than a century. Interest in this concept has never died; one example of a recent effort is the 1958–59 Library of Congress “cataloging in source” project, which the Council supported. In 1971, the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities awarded a grant to the Library of Congress to support a Cataloging in Publication (CIP) program. To date, CIP data has been prepared for over 200,000 titles, and currently appears in approximately 65% of the books published in the U.S. CIP has developed from a small charter group of 27 trade publishers to more than 2,000 active participants. It also has spread to publishers in other countries.

In 1980, after nine years of CIP activity, the Library of Congress requested, and the Council granted, funding to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of the program. During early 1981, about 2,400 U.S. libraries of all sizes and types were surveyed to determine the extent and type of their use of CIP data. About 80% reported using CIP data for some purpose—acquisitions, cataloging, or public services. The Cataloging in Publication Division anticipates preparation of a final report in the fall of 1981. Results will be used to improve and perhaps expand the service.⁶

⁶*Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 40 (August 14, 1981) p. 265–266.

Library Operations and Services

Central to assessing the current status of research libraries is an awareness of the increasingly varied array of library programs and services. Technological advances are responsible for many of the changes in operations and for the new services libraries offer. However, budget constraints keep many institutions from taking full advantage of their opportunities. Because choices among budget alternatives are both frequent and difficult, and because operational needs often conflict with user requirements, managing the research library has become a complicated task. All levels of governance have been affected, from the relationship between the library and its parent institution to the educational and training demands of online operations.

For a number of years, the Council has supported work aimed at improving management practices in individual libraries and at evaluating services and collections. This year, for example, a Council grant supported an American Library Association project to assess online search services in academic and research libraries. The college library's role in undergraduate education has been another major Council interest, as demonstrated in the College Library Program. An earlier section of this report details CLR efforts at expanding communication between librarians and scholars. This recent initiative promises to aid in enhancing library involvement in instruction and in assessing the unique requirements of the various academic disciplines.

Research Library Economics

Related to the interest in communicating library needs and increasing librarians' involvement in the instructional, budget and planning processes,

is a new Council-supported endeavor. Early in 1981, the Association of Research Libraries in cooperation with the Research Libraries Group, Inc., received CLR funds to explore research library economics and financing.

Several concerns prompted the ARL-RLG proposal. First, available cost data on library operations and services is not adequate to support efforts to improve research libraries' financial management. Second, the nature and dynamics of library-institutional relations have not been articulated. Finally, the economics of scholarly communication, which transcends library and institutional entities, deserves increased consideration in light of current financial strictures.

As a first step, ARL and RLG planned a meeting of invited participants to discuss the issues and to provide guidance on assessing library cost data, budgeting systems, and options for utilizing available information in making decisions. The meeting is expected to constitute the framework for a longer research effort.

Academic Library Program

Established in 1970, the Office of Management Studies of the Association of Research Libraries has led a number of efforts to improve management and fiscal practices in academic and research libraries. The OMS programs are grouped in four major categories: the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (an information clearinghouse); the OMS Training Program for library staff members, supervisors, and administrators; research projects; and the Academic Library Program (ALP).

In 1978, the Council provided a \$326,000 grant for the ALP with funds received from the Carnegie Corporation of New York. Parts of the program also are funded by the Lilly Endowment, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities, as well as by cost recovery from participants.

Within the Academic Library Program, the OMS staff assists individual libraries with planning and problem solving through the self-study method. This methodology first was employed to address general management issues. Using office program manuals, and with staff assistance, selected members of the library staff at each participating institution examine the demands and pressures of the current environment, assess the library's situation, and design recommendations for improvements in programs and activities.

The program now comprises eight major study areas, ranging from the original Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP) to the new program areas of preservation and public services. One of the most used programs has been the Collection Analysis Project. Seven of the twenty-eight libraries that participated in the ALP during 1980 chose collection analysis as a focus of concern. A relatively recent development has been the use of separate modules of individual studies. For example, participating libraries may choose to devote their resources to a two-to-three months'

study within the Collection Analysis Project, concentrating on topics such as history and development of the collection, materials fund allocations, or resource sharing. This arrangement allows completion of a study in about one-third less time than would be required for the full program.

During 1979, a new ALP program began with the selection of 20 librarians to participate in the OMS Consultant Training Program. The program provides an opportunity for individuals to develop skills in identifying and diagnosing library problems, to study theoretical and conceptual elements of library training and consultation, to gain experience in consulting, and to obtain an understanding of OMS self-study procedures and their application.

Consultant trainees are selected on the basis of written applications, interviews and participation in an assessment workshop. The criteria for selection are: five years of successful library experience; demonstrated skills in dealing with colleagues, communication, analysis of problems and decision making; openness to new ideas and tolerance for differing views; and the ability to devote up to 22 days to the program (on a released time or personal leave basis).

During 1980, each of the first 20 participants worked with OMS staff in a practicum experience which involved OMS training activities and co-consulting with OMS staff members conducting ALP studies. A second class of 20 trainees was selected from 159 applicants and trained in an intensive two-week workshop in March, 1981.

College Library Program

The College Library Program was established in 1969 by the Council on Library Resources and the National Endowment for the Humanities. By 1978, the program had awarded grants to 35 college and university libraries to explore ways to enhance library participation in undergraduate education. At the close of fiscal 1978, CLR and NEH discontinued the program, but because previous grants were for three to five year periods, final recipients will not complete the grant period until 1983. Nine programs remained active at the end of the fiscal year.

Each institution has developed its own goals and objectives. Success has been mixed, but student and faculty interest in program activities, and institutions' willingness to assume program costs after grant funds terminate imply that the overall results are good. Pacific University, completing the program in 1980, titled its activities "Maximum Instructional Effectiveness through Maximum Usage of Library Materials." The final report noted that the university had assumed support of the Study Skills Center established under the grant.

The University of Wisconsin-Parkside also conducted a successful program. In 1977/78 the university instituted a competency in library skills requirement to accompany its other competency requirements in reading, writing, and mathematics. Upon receiving the CLR grant, the library estab-

lished five project goals in support of the competency requirement. The goals included perfecting a library skills test, developing methods and materials for team teaching a research skills course, enhancing library-faculty relationships, and developing subject workbooks for bibliographic instruction in a number of disciplines.

The project evaluation noted that progress toward all goals was impressive: *"The NEH/CLR grant has helped Parkside expand, intensify and strengthen the bibliographic instruction program on three levels: orientation, basic library skills and course-integrated library instruction. It has contributed to the establishment of a model bibliographic instruction program—in a state-supported community-based commuter college library . . . Parkside's administration and staff have made a long term commitment to bibliographic instruction by establishing as its mission to be a teaching library. Short and long range planning is guided by this mission. The Library/Learning Center has been reorganized to support the concept of the teaching library through traditional and outreach services."*

The institutions at which libraries are still engaged in grant activities are: Johnson C. Smith University (N.C.), University of Evansville (Ind.), Northwestern University (Ill.), St. Olaf College (Minn.), Ball State University (Ind.), DePauw University (Ind.), Franklin and Marshall College (Pa.), Lake Forest College (Ill.), and Tusculum College (Tenn.).

Library Services

A major objective of the College Library Program is to integrate the library more closely into the curriculum, through librarian-faculty, and librarian-student interaction. In some instances the program has provided the impetus for continuing library-faculty collaborative efforts, and has enabled librarians to enter the classroom for the first time. Bibliographic instruction programs, constructed and implemented in a variety of ways, have been the principal means of promoting this cooperation. Through 1979 grants to Earlham College and the University of Wisconsin-Parkside, the Council has supported workshops as another means of bringing faculty, librarians and administrators together to discuss instructional activities.

A second grant to Earlham in 1980 provided funds to help defray expenses for twenty-five faculty members attending the College's fifth Conference on Bibliographic Instruction, held in April, 1981. That both faculty and librarian participants find the conferences helpful is shown by comments received after the fourth conference. One faculty participant wrote that *"I have many new ideas and am thoroughly convinced that librarians are valuable teaching assets."* Another enthusiastically noted, *"It was far superior to what I expected. I thought I'd find myself in a group narrowly committed to getting students to using the library. Instead I found a faculty (instructors and librarians together) committed to improving the quality of instruction, committed to enrich their students' experience."*

Online bibliographic searching is one of the most promising new service initiatives in many types of libraries. This service promises to advance libraries' ability to deliver information to users. In many cases, it serves as a pilot experiment in introducing technology to students, faculty and staff.

The question of how online search services should be financed, particularly in publicly supported libraries, has been a matter of debate ever since their introduction. Many libraries find it necessary to charge user fees for the service and there is a considerable diversity of practices and procedures in the absence of established guidelines on managing data base search services. After studying the question, the American Library Association proposed a research plan to assess the methods used by libraries to cover costs of online services and the Council granted funding for the project.

Through the major database vendors (Bibliographic Retrieval Services, Lockheed, and the System Development Corporation), ALA distributed questionnaires to libraries that use online search services. Both publicly supported libraries and libraries in noncommercial organizations and institutions are included, and results of the survey will be analyzed by the ALA Office for Research. The data is expected to be helpful in aiding libraries' decisions to introduce online services, encouraging improvement and expansion of existing services, and helping libraries plan other technological innovations in the services area.

Public and State Libraries

While the Council's primary focus is on academic and research libraries, it sometimes receives proposals that include other types of libraries as the subject for investigation or support. On occasion, the Council has funded such proposals because it feels that support of particular projects may contribute to broader goals for the profession as a whole. For example, in 1958, 1960, 1963, 1977 and 1980, funds were awarded to the Library of Congress to support the Assemblies of State Librarians. These meetings provide a channel of cooperation between state agencies and the Library of Congress that otherwise might not be available.

Another Council-supported project in this area is the 1980 grant to the Plainedge Public Library in Massapequa, New York, for a research study to learn more about motivating nonusers or infrequent users to increase their use of public libraries. Surveys of nonusers were conducted by a consultant, Dr. Ernest Dichter, a well-known authority in the field of motivational research. Study results currently are being evaluated by the library.

Archivists' Self Study

During 1980, the Society of American Archivists received CLR funding for a project to test procedures for institutional evaluation of archival agencies. Because very little formal, standardized preparation for archival work exists, the Society formulated evaluative criteria based on archives'

activities and services. Self-study plus an onsite visit by an experienced archivist are the basic components of the evaluation.

The SAA Task Force on Institutional Evaluation has to date formulated documentation for the self-study and review process and tested the procedures in six archival institutions: Cincinnati Historical Society, the Manuscripts Department of the University of Virginia Library, the Salvation Army Archives and Research Center, the Tennessee State Library and Archives, the Illinois State Archives, and the Sangamon State University Archives. Final results are being received and evaluated, and a formal report will conclude the project.

Library Resources and Their Preservation

One of the Council's oldest and best known interests is preservation of library materials. The level of concern among members of the profession, however, has not always matched that of the Council. During prosperous years, thoughts of collection deterioration received only marginal attention from librarians. Even disastrous floods in some European and American libraries did little more than spark an interest in freeze-drying wet books. Whether books crumbled in safe stacks, burned, or drowned by accident, preservation ranked low on priority lists—particularly in comparison with topics such as collection building.

In recent years, interest in preservation has increased. Possibly the seemingly greater frequency of accidents to collections has prompted this concern. However, it is more probable that the attention focused on preservation is a result of losses in library buying power. Most libraries can no longer afford to purchase a major portion of the output of even U.S. presses. Because librarians perceive that some materials will not be readily available locally, preserving copies of titles likely to be required for future use has become important.

For over a century, the majority of American books have been produced on acidic paper. There are several reasons for this. For example, alum and rosin are used to “size” the paper; that is, to treat it so that it will hold the inked impression. Another reason is that wood has been used as the source of cellulose fibers that are essential to paper manufacture. If wood is not purified to eliminate certain components, the paper produced from it is acidic. Experts disagree on the period of time that will elapse before paper deteriorates; however, according to the Library of Congress' Statement on Paper Durability, books printed on acidic paper will deteriorate in only 25

to 50 years.¹ Filming, restoring, recording, replacing or discarding are the alternatives for non-durable library materials, but all these procedures are costly. While librarians recently have been interested in establishing preservation units and encouraging efforts to train preservation specialists, they are beginning to realize that changing the quality of the book trade output is an essential accompaniment to preserving what has been produced.

Committee on Production Guidelines For Book Longevity

During a quarter century of research, the Council has supported a laboratory for chemical research on paper deterioration and the means of preventing it, sponsored efforts to develop specifications for selecting paper and bindings, and provided assistance for numerous meetings, studies and other efforts to found a national effort for preservation. In 1979, with the assistance of the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLR established the Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity.² Composed of publishers and librarians, the Committee has studied the book paper problem as a first step toward its goal of considering all aspects of book longevity. On February 26, 1981, the group held an all-day meeting at the Library of Congress under the auspices of the Center for the Book. Following the meeting, members drafted an *Interim Report on Book Paper*, issued in April, 1981.

The Committee's report has a dual purpose: to increase awareness of the problem and to establish guidelines to assure permanence and durability. Members noted that certain economic considerations and the appearance of anti-pollution laws have increased interest in the production of acid-free paper. In 1980, about one-fourth of the paper manufactured in the United States was acid-free, and this percentage is likely to increase during the next decade. Because the supply of acid-free paper continues to be limited, however, a major task is to determine what categories of material should receive priority in the production of acid-free books. Although publishers will have to make the final judgments, the Committee suggests that such decisions can be guided by professionals in the field and members of the scholarly community.

The Committee noted that neither publishers nor librarians have made permanence an important consideration in production and purchase decisions. The group recommends that publishers stock acid-free paper for use on appropriate titles, and that they carefully consider the kinds of paper used to print their books. In order to assure recognition of durable books,

¹"Library of Congress Statement on Paper Durability." Press release, Library of Congress, May 15, 1981. 4p.

² Members of the Committee are Herbert S. Bailey, Jr., Princeton University Press, Frank G. Burke, National Historical Publications and Records Commission, Warren J. Haas, Council on Library Resources, Inc., Peter Mollman, World Book, Leonard D. Schlosser, Lindenmeyr Paper Corporation, David H. Stam, New York Public Library, and R. Gay Walker, Yale University Library.

the Committee suggests that publishers identify acid-free books with an appropriate statement in each book. Recommendations addressed to the library community include taking responsibility for making publishers aware of preservation needs. The report also contains a list of paper manufacturers that produce acid-free paper, and guidelines for technical specifications for permanent paper.

During the next year, the Committee plans to address the topic of binding. However, its activities are not the only CLR-sponsored effort in the preservation area. Now in its second year, a grant to the University of Wyoming to assist production of *Conservation Administration News* is an additional CLR preservation support activity. The newsletter is edited by the university's library director.

Collection Development and Collection Management

As with preservation, the recent interest in collection management springs primarily from austerity. Collection development or collection building characterized much of the 1970's, but it seems likely that elements such as library response to institutional change, interdependence among libraries, and local evaluation and analysis of collections will be major trends in the 1980's.

To support the dissemination of ideas on collection management, the Council awarded a modest sum to the American Library Association to conduct a pilot collection management and development institute, in July, 1981. Designed to introduce academic collection development officers and acquisitions librarians to concepts and techniques in the area, the institute was planned by the Resources and Technical Services Division, Resources Section, Collection Management and Development Committee.

The program was designed as a pilot regional institute that may be replicated in other areas. Small group sessions and lectures dealt with the topics of local collection management as distinct from collection building, and interdependent collection development among libraries. In order to facilitate planning for subsequent regional institutes, the Committee is developing a package of forms and manuals used at the initial sessions.

Practical problems of collection development and management also required attention during fiscal 1981. With the reduction in funds for the Library of Congress field office in New Delhi, the South Asian acquisitions program operated at minimal cost to research institutions, had to be cut back in most libraries. In response to a request from the Association for Asian Studies, CLR provided funding for a workshop in March, 1981, to review alternative ways to maintain support for acquiring South Asian research materials.

Associated Colleges of the Midwest

In August, 1980, Arthur Miller, Jr., of Lake Forest College submitted the final report on the library collection use study funded earlier that year

by a Council grant. The objectives of the project were to provide inexpensive and easily implemented methods for gathering collection use data and to provide guidelines to assist in the analysis and use of the results in small academic libraries. During the spring of 1980, three approaches to gathering collection data were tested: shelf list sampling, circulation record sampling, and stack sampling. Three ACM libraries participated in the data gathering effort: Lake Forest College, Knox College, and St. Olaf College. A major result of the project was the production of a manual for conducting similar studies.

In early 1981, the Council awarded a grant to the Association of Research Libraries to review and test the study manual. The ARL Office of Management Studies will add a collection description methodology section to the manual, and the test will be conducted in four member libraries of the Cooperative College Library Center, an Atlanta-based cooperative processing unit for a group of historically black institutions.

The major purpose of this project is to strengthen the procedures of the study and provide a tested, refined program of wide interest and utility for college libraries. Each of the test libraries will develop systematic collection descriptions, apply one of the three collection use study methodologies in the ACM manual, and use the results to implement changes in the collections program. An advisory committee composed of the directors of the participating libraries, faculty members from each school, and the director of the Cooperative College Library Center, has been organized to assist the project.

Resources, Surveys and Guides

Some assistance for collection development aids and materials for librarians continued during fiscal 1981. Since 1975, CLR has supported a regular column evaluating new serials in *Choice* magazine, a book selection guide for college and university libraries. Also, CLR has provided funding to produce reference materials and guides. In 1980, Etta Arntzen and Robert Rainwater published their *Guide to the Literature of Art History* (Chicago, 1980). The book is designed to revise and update Mary W. Chamberlain's *Guide to Art Reference Books* (Chicago, 1959). A CLR grant supported preparation of the work, which lists about 40% of the titles in the 1959 edition, but with extensive revision of annotations. The number of pre-1959 titles has been reduced in order to provide space to list books published during the sixties and seventies.

In 1979, a grant was awarded to the University of Kentucky Research Foundation for a project to produce essays on prominent librarians whose careers spanned the 1925-75 period. In his proposal for this project, Dr. Wayne Wiegand, the coordinator, noted that little has been done to advance librarians' understanding of how the history of libraries has shaped the current professional environment. He proposed to evaluate professional traditions and decisions through biographical studies of the careers

of fifteen major academic library leaders. Both scholars and practitioners served as authors for the studies. The *Journal of Academic Librarianship* will publish some of the essays, and a book-length anthology will be issued at a later date.

Professional Education and Training

Every aspect of library professional education—quality, quantity, content, and other matters—has been a topic of ongoing professional debate. The context of recent discussions has been the financial difficulties and technological opportunities that research libraries will face during the 1980's. The major question is how ongoing changes in library administration, operations, and relations with other libraries and with parent institutions can be addressed in professional education programs. There are two major concerns: first, that truly exceptional candidates are not entering the profession, and second, that graduating students have not been prepared sufficiently to assume research library positions.

In order to assess current educational and other professional requirements, up to date information on the status of professional librarians is essential. The Council has long been interested in this topic, and it has funded a number of surveys on compensation structures for academic librarians. Results that confirmed the general impression that the profession does not reward its members highly suggested a need for special incentives to attract high quality candidates and to assist their professional development.

A CLR grant aided the American Library Association's Office for Library Personnel Resources to gather current information on the composition and salary structure of the library work force. Published in mid-1981, the survey results were issued as *The Racial, Ethnic and Sexual Composition of Library Staff in Academic and Public Libraries* (Chicago, 1981). The report is useful for affirmative action planning since it includes statistics on the composition of the library professional work force by race,

ethnicity and sex. Separate data for academic and public libraries and for individuals in selected positions are included.

During the late sixties and throughout the seventies, CLR programs included efforts to recruit specialists into the library field, to provide librarians with the opportunity to pursue advanced educational programs, and to encourage mid-career librarians to engage in research projects. Two intern programs, one for health science library interns and one for general management interns, were developed to help prepare promising candidates for leadership positions in academic and research libraries. Similarly, a writing seminar provided participants with an opportunity to improve their writing skills, exchange ideas, and review each others' work.

These efforts to provide programs not otherwise available to the profession were similar in that they focused upon individuals, and provided educational experiences within practical situations—through course work, intern arrangements, individual study or peer review. They provided assistance for many individuals and indirectly, to the profession, but no direct answer to questions on librarians' education and training.

One major concern has been that individuals who possess the library science degree have not received the kind of training that is needed for many research library positions. Much library school course work is generalized, and the curriculum has failed to respond to specialized or unique requirements. Consequently, new graduates require substantial on-the-job training and instruction in basic technical skills. For those who have not had library experience, fulfilling the requirements of the first professional position requires a learning period.

Related to the concern over the training provided by library school programs is the perceived need for more advanced study opportunities in special fields. A focus on interdisciplinary study provides many librarians with an additional master's degree and some acquaintance with the subject matter of an area other than library science. Many of these people become subject specialists in academic libraries. Proponents of interdisciplinary programs suggest that those who desire library management careers also might benefit from degree programs that involve relevant course work in other fields.

"Retooling" and continuing education became bywords of the 1970's. Providing opportunities for those in management positions to acquire new knowledge is another professional education concern. Although programs for specialists and training opportunities for specific technical requirements are available, the needs of upper level management have received less attention.

A fourth area of interest, and one that promises to attract increasing attention during the 1980's, is the relationship of research libraries to their institutions and to society. A focused effort is required to obtain assistance from specialists and to use their expertise in finding answers to the economic, political, technical and intellectual questions that relate to research

library needs. Such an effort would aid library professionals to understand the current climate of research and opinion that relates to institutions. It also would assist them to explore the frontiers of knowledge in this area.

Considering these interests, the Council proposed and the Board of Directors agreed at the May, 1980 meeting to an expansion of CLR activities in the area of professional education and training. Assisted by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the Carnegie Corporation, the Council has begun a program planned for an initial three-year period. An advisory committee has been established to assist project planning.¹

Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship

The name of the new program is the Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship Program (PETREL). The first work of the Advisory Committee has been to establish priorities for the program, to work with library schools in their efforts to design appropriate projects and to inform the library community of the project grants. Early decisions to concentrate on education and training issues that affect research libraries and to work with library schools reveal a focus on formal education programs. However, there is also an emphasis on practical opportunities and programs for librarians at different career stages.

Three library schools—the University of Chicago, the University of Michigan, and the University of California at Los Angeles—have been granted funds to carry out specific aspects of the PETREL program. The major portion of this funding is designated for the support of students because this appears to be the best way to attract well-qualified candidates. New proposals for the expansion of project activities continue to be reviewed by the committee.

The Graduate Library School at the University of Chicago, in cooperation with the Graduate School of Business, has established a special post-graduate program leading to a certificate of advanced study in library management. The course work includes interdisciplinary study in library science and management, a special seminar to continue throughout the period of study, and investigative internships at participating research libraries.

The School of Library Science at the University of Michigan has begun an active recruiting program designed to attract a small number of highly qualified candidates to specialize in research librarianship. An extended academic program, additional course work in related disciplines, research library internships and placement assistance are included in the new basic professional education program.

1. Members of the PETREL Advisory Committee are Russell Bidlack, University of Michigan, William Gerberding, University of Washington, Margot McBurney, Queens University, John McDonald, University of Connecticut, Rutherford Rogers, Yale University, and Robert Vosper, University of California, Los Angeles.

The Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of California, Los Angeles, has assumed responsibility for two projects. The first, designated a "Senior Fellows Program" provides an opportunity for specialized training for individuals who have recently assumed major management posts. A six-week course emphasizing managerial skills for research librarians with periodic follow-up sessions during the year of the fellowship will be developed as a prototype for a continuing program.

A second UCLA project is for a conference designed to explore and describe the frontiers of research librarianship. The objective of the initial week-long conference is to relate research library development and operations to the economic, technological, political and intellectual factors that promise to dominate policy making for the next decade. UCLA has been given support to host the first of a series of such conferences, to be attended by librarians, university administrators and others who have specialized skills pertinent to the agenda.

As the year ended, the new efforts were well under way and both Chicago and Michigan had established advisory committees to assist their progress. The PETREL advisory committee continues discussion on additional topics including support for research on major issues pertinent to research library management and operations. The theme of all activities is to provide distinctive opportunities for professional growth of exceptional research librarians, to develop improved capacities for professional education, and to establish and help carry out a research agenda for research libraries.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

An early indication of the Council's interest in professional education was the establishment of the Management Intern program eight years ago. The program is designed to assist the development of management skills of potential candidates for administrative positions in research and academic libraries. Applicants must be librarians who are U.S. or Canadian citizens or who have permanent resident status in either country. Most successful applicants enter the program with five years' professional library experience, usually including some administrative responsibility.

Each intern spends an academic year working closely with the director and administrative staff of a major academic library. The programs for individual interns vary, but the primary intention is to enable an intern to study how a director of a large library system handles responsibilities and deals with an array of long and short-term problems and issues.

Chosen from a class of 67 applicants, the 1981-82 class of interns brings to 35 the total number of participants in the program. This year, for the first time, two interns are assigned to one institution, the University of California at Los Angeles. The two are expected to work together on many projects.

The following interns were chosen to work with directors of four academic libraries during the 1981-82 academic year:

Anne W. LeClercq, associate professor and head of the undergraduate library at the University of Tennessee, Knoxville, will work with Russell Shank, University of California at Los Angeles. Ms. LeClercq received a B.A. from Duke University and the M.L.S. from Emory University. A CLR fellow in 1974, Ms. LeClercq's contributions to the literature include articles on non-print media and its library applications.

Patricia McClung will also work at UCLA with Russell Shank. Her career includes service at the Harvard University library, and since 1975 she has been with the Alderman Library, University of Virginia, as North American Bibliographer. Her library science degree is from Simmons College.

James G. Neal, head of the collection management department at the University of Notre Dame, will intern with Stuart Forth, director of libraries at Pennsylvania State University. His degrees are a B.A. in Russian Studies from Rutgers, and an M.A. in history and an M.S. in library science from Columbia University. He also has earned a certificate in advanced librarianship from Columbia.

Virginia F. Toliver is coordinator of computer assisted retrieval services at the University of Southern Mississippi. She will work with Charles Churchwell, dean of library services at Washington University. Formerly acting director at Alcorn State University Library, Lorman, Mississippi, Ms. Toliver received her M.L.S. from the University of Illinois.

Karen Wittenborg will work with Jay Lucker, director of libraries at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Her current responsibilities are as social sciences bibliographer and reference librarian, Stanford University. Formerly at the State University of New York at Buffalo, Ms. Wittenborg held several positions at that university and later moved to Albany as reference librarian and social sciences bibliographer. Her M.L.S. is from SUNY, Buffalo.

As the year ended, the Council decided not to select a class of interns for the 1982-83 academic year. Instead, the program will be suspended for a year in order to allow evaluation of its results and to assess future prospects in the context of PETREL projects. During the course of the review, the Council will request assistance from the librarians and hosts who have participated in the program, and from the PETREL advisory committee. Others also will be asked to contribute to the review, which is the first conducted since the beginning of the program.

Professional Education and Faculty Development

The three-year contract with the National Library of Medicine that supported the Health Sciences Management Intern Program ended with the

completion of the internships of the three librarians selected for 1980–81. However, the Council's interest in the special field of medical librarianship continues. Early in 1981, the Medical Library Association (MLA) received a PETREL grant to support the work of a study group designated by MLA to investigate the organization's role in the educational process for health sciences librarianship.

With partial funding from the National Library of Medicine, the Association and the University of Illinois Graduate School of Library Science sponsored a conference on the subject in April, 1979. The Conference, known as the Allerton Invitational Conference on Education for Health Sciences Librarianship, produced a number of recommendations regarding specialization, curriculum improvement, certification programs, post master's degree training, and the establishment of standards. A central issue was the need to secure more and better cooperation among library educators and practitioners to improve the quality of professional education.

The study group is charged with clarifying existing MLA policy, programs and commitments in light of the conference recommendations. It also will recommend long-range priorities, and mechanisms for supporting and implementing the priorities.

Archives management is another specialized field which has received Council attention. Most of the projects in this area relate to international archives activity. However, as a result of a Council grant this year, students at Wright State University gain practical experience through an internship program.

The University offers an M.A. degree in archival and historical administration. The program is designed to prepare students to seek employment as archivists, curators, or educational coordinators in historical societies, museums, government agencies and business firms. As part of the program, students have completed internships at local archival agencies. The CLR grant enabled the university to expand the internship program to national agencies and institutions. During the summer of 1981, students interned at the Chicago Historical Society, and at the National Archives and Records Service, in Washington, D.C.

Formal faculty development programs are relatively new in many academic institutions. However, faculty no less than practicing librarians are affected by the demands of new technology. Helping library school faculty to acquire new skills was the intent of a grant to C. W. Post Center of Long Island University. At Long Island, the library school wished to add course work in information science to the curriculum.

Because very few faculty members possessed the expertise to teach information science courses, the University planned a faculty development program. With funding from CLR and the Exxon Education Foundation, faculty from the Rutgers Graduate School of Library and Information Studies plus several C. W. Post faculty members conducted course work in basic information science for eleven faculty members during the year

1980–81. Five of the faculty are from C. W. Post; the other attendees are from St. John's University and Queens College. The goal of the project is to provide participants with sufficient knowledge and skills to be able to integrate information science into existing courses, and to teach introductory courses in information science.

New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar

In 1976, the Council awarded a grant to the University of Connecticut to support a writing seminar intended for practicing librarians. The project was designed to encourage the development of participants' writing skills through group interaction, peer review and criticism. The focus of the seminar was on writing for publication, and arrangements were made with *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* to publish some of the essays.

The final result of the Seminar appeared in 1980 with the publication by Scarecrow Press of *Essays from the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar*, edited by project director Norman D. Stevens. In addition to previously published articles from seminar members, the volume includes longer essays on the topics of financial planning, bibliographic instruction, online searching, information resources in the academic institution, automation of acquisitions, the corporate library in a cooperative setting, peer evaluation for academic librarians, and the cooperative use of library personnel.

International Programs

The vision of a national library system composed of a federation of compatible networks is of comparatively recent date. It follows that the idea for an international library system made up of national and multi-national networks, employing a variety of computerized and manual techniques is an even more current conception. Only in recent years has such a development seemed possible. Yet, over time, librarians have tried to effect international agreements on recorded and cataloged information so that there would be few impediments to exchange. Through international organizations, they have sought to improve technical knowledge and to assist library development throughout the world. Their cooperative efforts in automation and bibliographic control are another part of the general effort to standardize the exchange of bibliographic records and to facilitate the free flow of bibliographic information.

CLR has always conceived its role as seeking solutions to library problems without regard to geographic limits. In practice, this has meant providing assistance for activities designed to further cooperation, bibliographic development and communication among libraries all over the globe. The Council has worked with organizations, institutions, and individuals to promote basic work and communication necessary for further development. Major funding for these efforts during the last two years has come from the Exxon Education Foundation. During 1980, the foundation awarded CLR a second grant to support international activities.

Although the bulk of available funds has gone to major projects, there has been a deliberate effort through the years to provide for individual participation in international organizations. On occasion, small travel grants from general funds have gone to foreign librarians to allow them to

learn of U.S. developments, and to U.S. librarians to enable them to represent the United States at major foreign conferences or meetings. During this fiscal year, grants were provided to Foster Mohrhardt and Rutherford D. Rogers for travel to meetings of the IFLA Programme Management Committee, which they consecutively chaired. Dr. H.D.L. Vervliet, Librarian of the University of Antwerp, received a grant for a study visit to U.S. libraries. Also, the Library of Congress received assistance to allow a representative of the Library to attend the British Library conference on resource sharing held during April, 1981.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

Since the early 1970's, a major channel of CLR support for international library activities has been the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). Ongoing Council grants have supported the work of its secretariat and the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control. New grants provide funds primarily for special projects.

Founded in 1927, IFLA has served as a major forum for the discussion of library problems and as a coordinating body for international activities. In 1981, the association listed 990 institutional members, affiliates and library organization members in 111 countries. For a number of years, the organization has held consultative status in UNESCO.

In 1981, the Council granted funding to IFLA to cover travel and related costs for IFLA delegates to visit China to establish an active relationship with the People's Republic, especially in bibliographic matters. Invited by the China Society of Library Science, the IFLA delegates reported that their hosts are interested in becoming involved in international library cooperation.

In early 1979, the Council awarded IFLA a two-year grant for special projects including inquiries into copyrighting bibliographic records and files and conversion of copyrighted materials for use by handicapped readers.

Copyright and Library Materials for the Handicapped, a study prepared for IFLA by Françoise Hébert and Wanda Noel, was finished in January, 1981. The study examines the special nature of library services for the handicapped and identifies copyright problems that attend the production and dissemination of materials in special formats, such as Braille, audiotape and large print. Existing copyright legislation that includes special provisions for such materials and international copyright conventions are described as examples of possible legislative action. A series of recommendations for IFLA action concludes the analysis. Since 1981 is the International Year of Disabled Persons, the IFLA study appears at a particularly appropriate time to publicize the findings and implement the recommendations.

IFLA also has undertaken projects relating to copyright of machine-readable bibliographic records. Major concerns are the conditions of exchange among national bibliographic agencies, the commercial networks'

use of records provided by national bibliographic agencies, and the national agencies' legal responsibilities for distributing records received from other sources. Findings from IFLA studies in this area are pertinent to other CLR programs and projects, especially those within the purview of the Bibliographic Service Development Program.

In 1980, the Federation issued *International Access to MARC Records*. This publication includes the report of a survey of national bibliographic organizations regarding the international exchange of bibliographic records. Survey results indicate that the agencies support removing as many bureaucratic and financial barriers to such exchanges as possible. IFLA has contracted with King Research, Inc. to conduct a study to clarify the issues involved in international exchange of bibliographic records and to propose solutions to the problems.

The study is expected to address two sets of issues. The first set comprises questions that arise as national agencies begin to share machine-readable data among themselves. Examples of such questions are the extent to which legal provisions protect bibliographic files, the kinds of restrictions that exist in exchange agreements among agencies, and the mechanisms for recovering costs of bibliographic record development and exchange. The second group of issues relates to distribution and use of records outside the national agencies. These questions concern the definition of record ownership and control, protection for ownership rights, and the means of assuring an appropriate return on investment for both public and private sector agencies.

IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control

International cataloging agreements have been a major focus of IFLA effort for a number of years. In 1971, CLR awarded funds to support the work of the IFLA Cataloging Committee Secretariat which in 1973 presented a long-term program for developing a worldwide system for the exchange of bibliographic information based on the concept of Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC). In 1974, IFLA transformed the secretariat into the International Office for UBC and secured UNESCO approval of the concept as a major policy objective. Ever since that time, CLR has cooperated with the national libraries and bibliographic organizations in supporting the work of the office. Additional revenue comes from the sale of publications, contracts and consulting fees. The CLR grant expired in June, 1981.

The concept of universal bibliographic control is an essential element in international thinking about standardization and exchange of information. Both IFLA and UNESCO are working to develop a worldwide system for control and exchange of bibliographic information. Their goal is to make universally and promptly available in an internationally acceptable format bibliographic information on publications issued in all countries. This goal suggests the construction of an international bibliographic network. There

are two assumptions underlying this program: that individual countries are best able to identify and record their own national bibliographic information, and that acceptance of international bibliographic standards will provide a means of controlling production and exchange of records.

International Council on Archives (ICA)

Ongoing grants made possible by the Exxon Education Foundation supported funding for ICA projects during fiscal 1981. The theme of ICA activity has been the worldwide preservation and use of archival sources, with special attention to third world countries and newly independent nations. Three projects planned for the year were completed and another is scheduled for implementation in 1981. With CLR funding, ICA held a symposium at Rio de Janeiro in August, 1980, on the subject of advancing the status and professional development of archivists and records managers in Latin America, and in a related development, three separate model curricula for in-service training of archival personnel were completed. Designed for use in English, French, and Spanish speaking countries, the curricula were finished in early 1981.

A records management manual designed especially for use in recently independent countries also was published during 1980. Thomas W. Wadlow's *Disposition of Government Records* contains specifications and recommendations for records management in third world regions. In June, 1981, CLR made a further grant to ICA to test the manual at a regional seminar on the disposition of government records to be held in New Delhi, October 12–16, 1981. Another CLR-funded ICA project is the preparation of a basic text on administration of archival institutions. The text will emphasize organization, fiscal control and managerial practices. ICA intends to have the original Spanish text translated into English and French.

Training and Standardization

Much of the Council's activity on the international scene has involved standardization and extension of library practices and procedures. In line with that interest, a small grant was made to the Forest Press, Albany, N.Y., publisher of the Dewey Decimal Classification, to provide partial support for direct costs associated with investigating the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey classification.

A grant to the Lesotho Library Association enabled the Association to hold a five-day workshop involving librarians, library school faculty and school administrators. The workshop focused on drawing up a curriculum for professional education for school librarians. The proposed curriculum will be incorporated into teacher training programs in Lesotho.

Publications Resulting From CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships, 1980–1981

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Creth, Sheila D. "Manpower Planning, Job Analysis and Job Evaluation." November, 1980. (CLR Fellow, 1979–1980)

Halporn, Barbara. "Libraries and Printers in the Fifteenth Century." *Journal of Library History* 16 (Winter, 1981) 134–142. (Advanced Study Fellow, 1976–1977)

ACTIVE PROJECTS

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1981 (unaudited)

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities Washington, D.C.				
AAAHA/ARL sponsored meeting of research librarians and scholars	\$ -0-	\$ 1,500	\$ 1,000	\$ 500
American Library Association Chicago, Ill.				
Ethnic and sexual compo- sition/salary survey for librarians	6,928	-0-	6,928	-0-
Collection management institute	-0-	5,150	4,000	1,150
Financing online search services	-0-	7,110	5,000	2,110
Associated Colleges of the Midwest, Chicago, Ill.				
Manual to guide study of collection use in small academic libraries	26,553	2,100 (3,383)	25,270	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program	203,500	-0-	60,000	143,500
Collection assessment for small academic libraries	-0-	11,200	-0-	11,200
ARL/RLG joint project on decision support systems for libraries	-0-	30,000	15,000	15,000
Association for Asian Studies, Inc., Ann Arbor, Mich.				
South Asia Library Workshop	-0-	4,500	4,000	500
Boston Theological Institute Cambridge, Mass.				
Two-year serial cataloging project	2,582	-0-	2,582	-0-

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Council of National Library and Information Associations				
Haverford, Pa.				
Continued support of the American National Standards Committee Z-39	\$ 15,000	\$ -0-	\$ 15,000	\$ -0-
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind.				
Periodical list for <i>Choice</i>	2,200	-0-	-0-	2,200
5th Conference on Bibliographic Instruction	-0-	5,900 (473)	5,900 (473)	-0-
Forest Press, Albany, N.Y.				
Investigation of the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification	-0-	6,000	-0-	6,000
International Council on Archives				
Paris, France				
Special projects	15,000	3,464	15,464	3,000
Additional projects	-0-	20,000	-0-	20,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands				
Professional activities of the secretariat	30,000	-0-	30,000	-0-
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control	31,756	-0-	28,000	3,756
Special projects	64,000	-0-	22,000	42,000
Costs to establish IFLA/P.R.C. liaison	-0-	5,000	4,000	1,000
Lesotho Library Association				
Lesotho, Africa				
Workshop for training school librarians	-0-	5,500	5,000	500
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Fifth Assembly of State Librarians	-0-	(1,678)	(1,678)	-0-
Travel grant for L.C. representative at British conference on resource sharing	-0-	1,000	-0-	1,000
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication program	-0-	11,000	11,000	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/80	FY 1981		Unpaid 6/30/81
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
MIDLNET, Chicago, Ill.				
Toward salary of a technical advisor	\$ 17,778	\$ (19,278)	\$ (1,500)	\$ -0-
Foster Mohrhardt, Arlington, Va.				
Travel grant to chair IFLA Program Management Committee	4,688	(4,575)	113	-0-
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advance- ment of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga.				
Status report on libraries of black public colleges	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C.				
College Library Program	-0-	(933)	(933)	-0-
Plainedge Public Library Massapequa, N.Y.				
Research to determine reasons for nonuse of public libraries	9,750	-0-	-0-	9,750
C. W. Post Center of Long Island University, Greenvale, N.Y.				
Faculty development project in information science	-0-	10,000	9,000	1,000
Rutherford D. Rogers New Haven, Conn.				
Travel grant to chair IFLA Program Management Committee	-0-	6,000	2,800 (669)	3,869
Society of American Archivists, Chicago, Ill.				
Pilot project for self-study and peer review of archives	18,670	-0-	9,000	9,670
University of California, Berkeley, Cal.				
National shelflist measurement project	8,293	-0-	-0-	8,293
University of California, Los Angeles, Cal.				
Third edition of <i>Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries</i>	9,500	-0-	-0-	9,500

	Unpaid 6/30/80	FY 1981		Unpaid 6/30/81
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of Kentucky, Lexington, Ky.				
Preparation of "Leaders in American Academic Librar- ianship 1925-75"	\$ 6,000	\$ -0-	\$ 2,000	\$ 4,000
University of Wyoming, Laramie, Wyo.				
Support of <i>Conservation Administration News</i>	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000
Wright State University Dayton, Ohio				
Internships for master's degree students in archival and historical administration	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
Subtotals	477,698	135,424 (30,320)	285,557 (5,253)	302,498

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Academic Library Management				
Intern Program				
1978-79	\$ 590	\$ (40)	\$ 550	\$ -0-
1979-80	5,810	(2,119)	3,691	-0-
1980-81	111,639	-0-	85,740	25,899
	<u>118,039</u>	<u>(2,159)</u>	<u>89,981</u>	<u>25,899</u>
Bibliographic Service				
Development Program				
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Ill.				
LAWNET planning meeting	2,500	(216)	2,284	-0-
Richard Anable, Binghamton, N.Y.				
Preparation of a position paper on holdings statements	-0-	2,600 (59)	2,541	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
ARL microform project	-0-	20,000	-0-	20,000
Battelle Memorial Institute- Columbus Laboratories Columbus, Ohio				
Study of linking of biblio- graphic utilities	62,208	-0-	62,208	-0-
Training in the use of the BIBLINK model	-0-	15,068	4,009	11,059
Augmentation of the BIBLINK model and preparation of a users' guide	-0-	16,500	16,500	-0-
Dartmouth College Library Hanover, N.H.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs— Phase 2	-0-	12,919	-0-	12,919
Howard Harris & Patricia Harris Silver Spring, Md.				
Position paper on an institution identi- fication code standard	2,000	-0-	1,334	666
Institute for Research in Social Science, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Machine-readable data files cataloging manual	1,998	-0-	1,750	248

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Conversion of retrospective name authority file	\$165,000	\$ -0-	\$102,000	\$ 63,000
Travel costs re. the linked authority system project 1980 (with RLG & WLN)	17,000	(9,791)	7,948 (739)	-0-
Travel costs re. the linked authority system project 1981 (with RLG & WLN)	-0-	21,000	828	20,172
Travel grant for U.S. representative at Copenhagen meeting on an international authority system	1,105	(32)	1,073	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs—Phase 2	-0-	16,351	5,000	11,351
Carol Mandel & Judith Herschman				
Subject Access Paper	-0-	2,500	2,500	-0-
J. Matthews & Associates				
Grass Valley, Calif.				
Participant in joint project to define standard data elements & data collection methods for online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	9,500	7,375	2,125
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs—Phase 2	-0-	99,500	-0-	99,500
Northwestern University				
Evanston, Ill.				
Development of an application level protocol	-0-	36,000	-0-	36,000
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs— Phase 2	-0-	25,260	-0-	25,260
OCLC Inc., Dublin, Ohio				
Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (joint project with RLG)	2,150	-0-	2,150	-0-
Participant in joint pro- ject to define standard data elements & data col- lection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	25,000	22,500	2,500

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Pittsburgh Regional Library Center, Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Serials cancellation project	\$ -0-	\$ 24,000	\$ -0-	\$ 24,000
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Troy, N.Y.				
Planning a thesaurus for the fields of art & architecture	10,000	-0-	6,944	3,056
The Research Libraries Group, Inc., Stanford, Cal.				
Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (joint project with OCLC)	2,150	(12)	2,138	-0-
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN & LC) Phase 1	126,488	-0-	126,488	-0-
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN & LC) Phase 2	-0-	165,542	41,386	124,156
Inclusion of three research libraries in preliminary work for online public access catalog project: Joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	19,892	18,000	1,892
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs— Phase 2	-0-	116,614	-0-	116,614
James E. Rush Associates, Powell, Ohio				
Preparation of a paper on the role of regional networks	-0-	10,425 (22)	10,403	-0-
Norman B. Stevens, Storrs, Conn.				
Preparation of a paper on the role of regional networks	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Stanford University Libraries Stanford, Cal.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs— Phase 2	-0-	20,960	-0-	20,960

	Unpaid 6/30/80	FY 1981		Unpaid 6/30/81
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of California, Berkeley, Cal.				
Participant in joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	\$ -0-	\$ 5,650	\$ 5,100	\$ 550
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs—Phase 2	-0-	22,000	-0-	22,000
Analysis of data collected in the online catalog evaluation project—Phase 3	-0-	113,000	-0-	113,000
University of Illinois, Urbana, Ill.				
Statistical analysis of MARC database.	23,463	-0-	7,893	15,570
Washington Library Network, Olympia, Wash.				
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) Phase I	112,250	-0-	20,000	92,250
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) Phase 2	-0-	182,197	-0-	182,197
Total Bibliographic Service Development Program	528,312	1,012,328 (10,132)	507,352 (739)	1,023,895
Fellowship Program	13,710	(4,510)	3,380	5,820
Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program				
1979-80	11,632	(6,145)	6,537 (1,050)	-0-
1980-81	-0-	86,500	81,678	4,822
Library Service Enhancement Program				
Hampton Institute Hampton, Va.	1,742	(1,011)	731	-0-

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL)				
Medical Library Association, Chicago, Ill.				
Study group in education for health sciences librarianship	\$ -0-	\$ 2,000 (559)	\$ 1,441	\$ -0-
University of California, Los Angeles, Cal.				
Senior Fellows Program	-0-	125,000	-0-	125,000
Frontiers Conference	-0-	90,000	-0-	90,000
University of Chicago, Chicago, Ill.				
Special program of advanced study in library management	-0-	250,000	15,000	235,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Basic professional education for research librarianship	-0-	275,000	2,000	273,000
Total PETREL	-0-	742,000 (559)	18,441	723,000
Travel assistance				
H.D.L. Vervliet, University of Antwerp, Belgium				
Study trip to U. S. research libraries	-0-	2,500	500	2,000
Total CLR Projects	673,435	1,843,328 (24,516)	708,600 (1,789)	1,785,436
Subtotals page 53	477,698	135,424 (30,320)	285,557 (5,253)	302,498
TOTALS	\$1,151,133	\$1,978,752 (54,836)	\$994,157 (7,042)	\$2,087,934

Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered Projects (unaudited)

June 30, 1981

	Appropriated Balance 6/30/80	Appropriations (Restored) to Funds)	Awards (Restored to Approp- riations)	Project Costs Paid	Appropriated Balance 6/30/81
CONSER	\$ 2,880			\$ 1,021	\$ 1,859
Academic Library Management Intern Program					
1979-80	3,262	\$(3,262)			-0-
1980-81	10,655			6,441	4,214
1981-82	148,544			11,971	136,573
Travel by U.S. librarians	953				953
Foreign travel by U.S. librarians	1,081				1,081
U.S. travel by Foreign librarians	4,200		\$2,500		1,700
Preservation meetings	3,102	2,000		4,585	517
Totals	<u>\$174,677</u>	<u>\$ 2,000</u> <u>(3,262)</u>	<u>\$2,500</u>	<u>\$24,018</u>	<u>\$146,897</u>

Opinion of Independent Accountant

September 4, 1981

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1981, and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, and of changes in cash and short-term investments for the year then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1981, and the results of its operations and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied.

Our examination was made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances, by similar procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of financial position, results of operations and changes in cash and short-term investments, this information is submitted as additional data.

Price Waterhouse & Co.
Washington, D.C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Balance Sheet

JUNE 30, 1981

ASSETS

Cash and short-term investments	\$2,560,919
Grants receivable (Note 2)	4,532,687
Prepaid expenses and deposits	27,235
	<u>\$7,120,841</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Deferred income (Note 2)	\$3,770,961
Grants and contracts payable	2,087,934
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	42,472
Federal excise taxes payable	5,063
Total liabilities	<u>5,906,430</u>
Unrestricted fund balance	
Appropriated	\$ 146,897
Unappropriated	1,067,514
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$7,120,841</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1981

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Revenues (Note 2)			
Grants and contracts	\$ 700,000	\$2,081,519	\$2,781,519
Investment income	252,897		252,897
Royalty income	268		268
Total revenues	<u>953,165</u>	<u>2,081,519</u>	<u>3,034,684</u>
Expenses (Notes 2 and 3)			
Program services	265,713	2,081,519	2,347,232
Administrative services	273,670		273,670
Total expenses	<u>539,383</u>	<u>2,081,519</u>	<u>2,620,902</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	413,782		413,782
Fund balance, beginning of year	<u>800,629</u>		<u>800,629</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$1,214,411</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$1,214,411</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1981

Sources of cash and short-term investments

Excess of revenues over expenses	\$ 413,782
Increase in grants and contracts payable	936,801
Decrease in grants receivable	1,466,571
	<u>2,817,154</u>

Use of cash

Decrease in deferred income	2,216,519
Decrease in federal excise taxes payable, accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	2,664
Increase in prepaid expenses and deposits	18,473
	<u>2,237,656</u>

Increase in cash and short-term investments	579,498
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	1,981,421
	<u>\$2,560,919</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1981

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through two five-year unrestricted general support grants from The Ford Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and through several restricted grants and contracts from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 2% excise tax on investment and royalty income under the provisions of the Revenue Act of 1978.

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements are prepared on an accrual basis. Grants are recorded as receivable at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Interest and royalty income are recognized as unrestricted grant revenue. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses. Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. All unrecognized grant revenue is recorded as deferred income.

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

3. Functional Allocation of Expenses

The Council's costs of providing program and administrative services for the year ended June 30, 1981 are summarized in the schedule that follows.

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Expenses			
Program services			
Grants and contracts	\$ 67,960	\$1,910,792	\$1,978,752
Council-administered projects	24,000	187,563	211,563
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and contracts	(38,000)	(16,836)	(54,836)
Compensation and employee benefits	195,301		195,301
Other expenses	16,452		16,452
	<u>265,713</u>	<u>2,081,519</u>	<u>2,347,232</u>

Administrative services

Compensation and employee benefits	134,924		134,924
Rent	49,249		49,249
Travel	26,938		26,938
Other	62,559		62,559
	<u>273,670</u>		<u>273,670</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$539,383</u>	<u>\$2,081,519</u>	<u>\$2,620,902</u>

4. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$46,000 for fiscal year 1981.

5. Commitments

The Council is committed to a lease for office space expiring in 1982 which provides for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$50,000.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1981

1. Allocation of Expenses

Under the terms of the Ford and Mellon Foundations' unrestricted general support grants, the Council must account for expenditures of these funds on an individual basis. The Council allocates these expenses between the Ford and Mellon grants based upon the ratio of the sums of the respective fund balances at the beginning of the year and current year's revenue. Unrestricted expenses related to investment and royalty income are excluded from the Ford and Mellon allocation process.

2. Bibliographic Service Development Program

The Council has been awarded restricted grants totalling \$4,700,000 for this program from the following sources: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, The Commonwealth Fund, The Ford Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The purpose of these grants is to fund a five-year research and development project to assist in establishing primary components of a national bibliographic system. The Council currently estimates the costs of this project to be \$6,100,000. Additional funding from various sources will be sought as the project progresses.

3. CLR Review

A restricted grant from The Ford Foundation has been received by the Council to conduct a review of past and present CLR functions and to consider its future mission.

4. Health Sciences Management Intern Program

Under a three-year contract with the National Library of Medicine, which ends in 1981, the Council administers an internship program for mid-career health sciences librarians.

5. International Programs

During 1979 and 1980 the Council was awarded two restricted grants totalling \$200,000 from the Exxon Education Foundation in general support for the Council's international activities.

6. Management Programs

A \$500,000 restricted grant from the Carnegie Corporation of New York funds programs to improve the management of research libraries.

7. Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship

The Council has been awarded two restricted grants totalling \$1,100,000 from the Carnegie Corporation of New York and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to partially fund a new program of professional education and training for research librarians. Additional funding is being sought to meet the full cost of the program.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

PROGRAM GUIDELINES

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (CLR) is a private operating foundation. Established in 1956 by the Ford Foundation, the Council continues to receive support from it as well as other foundations. Over the years, the Council has sought to be of assistance to those who are concerned with the quality of library operations and the character of library service. From the beginning, CLR focused on academic and research libraries because they are important not only in themselves but to a wide segment of the population. Through research, development, demonstration, and dissemination of results, the Council seeks to reduce obstacles that hamper those who need and seek information.

How CLR Works

The Council awards grants to individuals and organizations for projects that fall within CLR program interests and hold promise of meeting stated goals. As an operating foundation, the Council also initiates and administers a limited number of specific programs. Occasionally, the Council enters into contractual arrangements.

CLR acts as a catalyst, often bringing together the expertise of many people and organizations for mutual exploration of a major issue. It is a coordinating agency, organizing participation in certain cooperative undertakings. Finally, it provides consultation services when requested in areas where help is needed but funding is either not sought or not possible.

Program Interests

To help identify problems that appear to be most pressing, certain key questions are periodically posed. How can a national bibliographic structure be built so that anyone requiring information can identify and locate what is required with reasonable ease and at an acceptable cost? How can the management and internal operations of libraries be improved so that the library patron can make efficient use of collections and human resources? How can the nation's library collections be preserved as a national resource and yet made widely available?

What is needed in terms of professional education and training for academic and research librarians and library managers? What is the role of the academic library in higher education and how can that partnership be enhanced? What kinds of basic information and analysis do we need about library economics, library relationships to other components of the information community, library staffing and collections, etc., that will help libraries improve their performance in support of research and instruction? While the answers to such questions may be uncertain, the simple process of asking them helps to identify problem categories needing attention. Certain of these topics become focal points of CLR program concerns. Those concerns presently include:

- bibliographic services
- library resources and their preservation

- library operations and services
- professional education and training
- research and analysis

Proposals are reviewed internally in accordance with established procedures. In addition, the Council frequently involves consultants in the evaluation of proposals on a confidential basis.

What Will Not Be Funded

No foundation can support all the legitimate needs of libraries. From the beginning the Council has established a policy of not providing support for certain categories of activity in order to concentrate on programs where funding is either limited or nonexistent. Thus CLR does not entertain proposals for building construction or improvement, purchase of collections or equipment, or normal staffing or operational costs. In addition, because the Council attempts to support programs that will result in benefits to many libraries, grants are not provided for programs that will be useful only to the institutions in which they take place.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries regarding possible project support should be in the form of a letter, which should include the following information:

1. Name and address of requesting individual or organization and name of proposed principal investigator
2. Type of institution
3. Tax status
4. A clear statement of the aims of the project and its significance, including details of the general approach and specific research methods to be used
5. Amount of request and proposed budget
6. Period to be covered by project

With this information, the project can be evaluated in terms of how it fits the Council's current program priorities. If a proposal is judged to be of possible interest, advice will be offered as to proposal preparation and additional information may be requested. There are no deadlines for general grant applications. All inquiries should be addressed to Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, 1 Dupont Circle, Suite 620, Washington, D.C. 20036.

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